

FINANCIAL ATTITUDES AND SPENDING HABITS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS IN TACURONG NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL: IMPLICATIONS FOR POVERTY REDUCTION AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT (SDG 1)

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 10

Pages: 1168-1173

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2130

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13201036

Manuscript Accepted: 06-25-2024

Financial Attitudes and Spending Habits of Senior High School Teachers in Tacurong National High School: Implications for Poverty Reduction and Sustainable Development (SDG 1)

El Jhon V. Sanoy Jr.,* Anjelica Dew O. Oro, Rachel Ruellen N. Zaide,
Maria Ericka Cazzandra S. Fernandez, Jose T. Decena III
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The research conducted an in-depth analysis of the financial attitudes and spending habits of 55 Senior High School (SHS) teachers at Tacurong National High School (TNHS) using a quantitative research design and descriptive correlational technique. The study questionnaire was adapted and contextualized. Mean, Pearson Moment Correlation, and Multiple Regression Analysis were used to examine the collected data. The results revealed high levels of retention-time (saving) and anxiety, a low level of power prestige, and a moderate level of distrust frugality in the financial attitude domains. Meanwhile, the spending habits domains showed a moderate level of diversity and overspending and a high level of loyalty. The study result showed a low positive correlation between financial attitudes and spending habits. However, no single domain of financial attitudes was found to significantly influence spending habits. The findings of this study bear significant implications for Sustainable Development Goal number one: No Poverty, as understanding the financial attitudes and spending habits of educators can aid in developing targeted interventions to enhance financial literacy, promote sustainable economic behaviors, and contribute to poverty reduction efforts.

Keywords: *teachers, financial attitudes, spending habits, multiple regression analysis*

Introduction

Teaching is a challenging career where meeting requirements demands both time and effort. Their pay check is the sole source of their financial commitments. They must not only look after themselves, they will occasionally combine assets and invest money to give an outstanding education for their students (Marasigan et al., 2022). Nowadays, uncontrollable spending habits toward people are increasing. Given the financial difficulties that emerging adults are currently experiencing, it is critical to investigate their spending habits. This is concerned with how a person, such as public secondary school educators, spends money to get and sustain financial security (Fry et al., 2020). According to Abaya et al. (2021), teachers are prone than other professions to take out substantial loans to support their daily necessities and wants while also improving their level of life.

In the study of Hristoski et al. (2019), understanding spending habits can greatly aid people in making better judgments because these are based on many soft financial transactions. It is the act of using one's money for a particular activity, such as making a purchase of goods or vices. In addition, a good spending habit is an essential instrument for financial success. Making wise spending decisions helps you reach your financial goals and makes your money work harder for you (Bona, 2018). Having the best spending habits is another element that could influence financial satisfaction. Therefore, the ability of an individual to manage their own finances in order to make wiser financial decisions and improve their financial circumstances is a prerequisite for financial pleasure (Azmi & Ramakrishnan, 2018).

According to Marasigan et al. (2022), financial attitudes sometimes have a significant effect, particularly gative, on one's spending habits because spending is frequently a habit. Furthermore, the results show that spending habits and financial attitude are statistically significantly correlated. based on the findings. Financial struggles have an impact on the spending habits of college students (Obagbuwa and Kwenda, 2020). Additionally, as noted by Kamil and Istianingsih (2020), their research demonstrates a strong direct relationship between spending patterns and lifestyle choices and financial attitudes.

Spending habits include not just what is actually spent but also what is saved and borrowed (Jamilah et al., 2021). The reason for conducting this study at Tacurong National High School is A descriptive-correlational study regarding the association between financial attitudes and spending habits was yet to be used to conduct a study on teachers at Tacurong National High School in the said locale. This study attempts to bridge the gap between the financial attitudes and spending habits of teachers at Tacurong National High School. This research helps to achieve Sustainable Development Goal 1 (SDG 1) of reducing poverty indirectly by addressing financial issues faced by teachers. Educators may contribute to the general objective of eradicating poverty by improving their economic well-being and reducing financial stress via improved money management. Together with evaluating instructors' financial attitudes, this will solve significant problems with spending patterns such improper allocation and overspending.

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the association between Tacurong National High School teachers' financial attitudes and spending habits. The following are the precise goals of this study:

1. To assess the level of financial attitude in terms of:

- 1.1. power-prestige;
- 1.2. distrust-frugality;
- 1.3. retention-time(saving); and
- 1.4. anxiety
2. To measure the level of teachers' spending habits in terms of:
 - 2.1. loyalty;
 - 2.2. diversity; and
 - 2.3. overspending
3. To determine the relationship between financial attitude and spending habits of Teachers at TNHS.
4. To determine which domains of financial attitude influence spending habits of Teachers at TNHS.

Methodology

Research Design

This study uses a quantitative study design, namely a descriptive-correlational technique. Descriptive studies, as outlined by Siedlecki (2020), aim to depict individuals, events, or conditions in their natural state. Complementing this, a correlational study relies on diverse statistical tests to unveil coefficients of correlation between variables. These coefficients are expressed mathematically to indicate the strength and direction of a relationship, as emphasized by Alston (2017). In the context of this study, we will explore the association between financial attitudes and the spending habits of Teachers at TNHS.

Respondents

The respondents were selected by non-probability sampling. Purposive sampling was used in selecting the respondents. Using a non-probability selection method called "purposive sampling," the researcher selects only those participants who, in their judgment, contribute to the goals of the study. With this approach, the researcher chooses study subjects at his own choice (Obilor 2023).

At Tacurong National High School (TNHS), there are 63 senior high school teachers. Based on Raosoft's calculations, which assume a 95% level of confidence, a 5% margin of error, and 50% of the answer distribution, 55 of these teachers are considered to be respondents in this study. In addition, participants had to fulfill two requirements in order to be eligible to participate in this study: (a) they had to be employed as senior high school teachers at Tacurong National High School (TNHS) and (b) they had to have at least three (3) months of teaching experience. Since the researchers used the purposive sampling method, they determined that having three (3) months of teaching experience was sufficient to be qualified to serve as a respondent in the study. Respondents could refuse to answer the questions or withdraw when they felt uncomfortable, intimidated, threatened, or perceived physical, emotional, or psychological harm.

Instruments

The financial attitudes survey was modified from one by Marasigan et al. (2022). This test is intended to assess the financial attitude of TNHS instructors according to four criteria: anxiety, distrust-frugality, power-prestige, and retention-time (saving). The spending habits survey was modified from the research by Marasigan et al. (2022). The tool is intended to assess TNHS teachers' spending habits according to three criteria: overspending, diversity, and loyalty.

Procedure

In obtaining the data needed for the study, many procedures were used. The first procedure was to obtain authorization to conduct the study, which was obtained first by asking permission from the principal office. The questionnaire was validated by professional validators. After the questionnaire was validated, the researcher tested it in a pilot with instructors from other departments.

Two professionals validated the questionnaires, and the results of the validated questionnaire obtained a score of 4.50, indicating that the questionnaire's content was rated as "Very Good". After the questionnaire had been validated, a pilot test was conducted with twenty (20) junior high school teachers from Tacurong National High School, Tacurong City, Sultan Kudarat. The questionnaire's reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, which measures the consistency coefficient ranging from zero to one. The following criteria are typically used to evaluate the validity of a questionnaire using Cronbach's alpha, as described by Darren and Mallery (1999): Alpha values of 0.8 or higher are considered good, while 0.9 or higher are excellent. A value of 0.7 is seen as acceptable, with 0.6 being questionable, and 0.5 indicating poor reliability. Values of 0.4 or lower are deemed unacceptable. In the pilot testing, the independent variable, financial attitude, demonstrated a Cronbach alpha score of 0.86, falling into the "Good" range. Conversely, the dependent variable, spending habits, also achieved a "Good" Cronbach alpha value of 0.81.

Data Analysis

The data that was gathered from the questionnaires and handled and evaluated using the following statistical tools:

Mean. This was done to ascertain the teacher's spending habits and financial attitude at TNHS.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation. This was applied to establish the weight of the correlation between financial attitude and

spending habits.

Multiple Regression. It was used to find out which aspect of financial attitude affects the TNHS teachers' spending habits.

Results and Discussion

Level of Financial Attitude

Table 1 shows the level of Financial Attitude of teachers at Tacurong National High School. The overall mean score obtained for financial attitude is 3.15, indicating a moderate level. It means that the financial attitude of teachers is sometimes observed.

Table 1. *Level of Financial Attitude of Teachers*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Power-prestige	2.19	Low
Distrust-frugality	2.91	Moderate
Retention-time (saving)	3.99	High
Anxiety	3.50	High
Overall	3.15	Moderate

Level of Spending Habits

Table 2 lists the spending habits of the teachers. Three indicators—loyalty, diversity, and overspending—were given excellent descriptive ratings. The mean rating of 3.78 was given to loyalty, followed by 3.30 for overspending and 3.18 for diversity. The high level of 3.42 for the overall mean rating for spending habits indicates that instructors' spending habits are frequently observed.

Table 2. *Level of Spending Habits*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Loyalty	3.78	High
Diversity	3.18	Moderate
Overspending	3.30	Moderate
Overall	3.42	High

Significant Relationship between Financial Attitude and Spending Habits

Table 3 shows the noteworthy correlation between Tacurong National High School teachers' financial attitudes and spending patterns. Table 3 demonstrates a direct relationship between teachers' financial attitudes and spending habits at Tacurong National High School. This connection was determined by Pearson's Product Moment analysis of the data. The first null hypothesis of the study is rejected given the table and the calculated p-value of less than 0.001, which is lower than the threshold for significance of 0.05, showing that there is in fact a significant association between teachers' spending habits and financial attitude.

Table 3. *Significant relationship between Financial Attitude and Spending Habits*

<i>Category</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>Significant</i>
Financial Attitude Vs Spending Habits	P<0 .001	.440**	Low Positive Correlation

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Multiple Regression Analysis of the Financial Attitude Domains towards Spending Habits

Table 4 displays the Multiple Regression Analysis of the financial attitude domains regarding spending habits. The table shows the findings of a multiple regression study looking at the association between several financial attitude dimensions and spending habits. Each financial attitude category, anxiety, distrust-frugality, power-prestige, and retention-time (saving), was examined for its role in predicting spending behaviors. A p-value greater than a specific threshold (typically 0.05) indicates statistically insignificant influence. The table demonstrates that the p-values for all indicators are more than 0.05, indicating that no domain of financial attitude has a significant influence on spending patterns. Therefore, the second null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 4. *Multiple Regression Analysis of the Financial Attitude Domains towards Spending Habits*

	<i>Spending Habits</i>	
<i>Financial Attitude</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
Power-Prestige	.715	Not Significant
Distrust-Frugality	.265	Not Significant
Retention-Time (Saving)	.816	Not Significant
Anxiety	.054	Not Significant

Level of Financial Attitude

Two indicators show a high degree of financial attitude, the retention-time (saving), and anxiety. The moderate level is attributed to one indicator, distrust- frugality. The low level is attributed to one indicator, power-prestige. This means that the financial attitude of teachers in Tacurong National High school is sometimes observed. As stated by Fallaw (2021) financial attitudes are a spectrum encompassing negative to positive affective responses to individual monetary situations and challenges in financial planning. According to this characterization, our attitude toward managing finances emerges as the culmination of experiences, emotions, beliefs, and behaviors. Adding to the study's findings, a financial attitude is the inclination of a person to be economically ready for the future, showing a propensity to save money and control spending wisely (Utkarsh et al., 2020).

Level of Spending Habits

The high level of spending habits is attributed to one indicator, loyalty. The moderate level is attributed to two indicators, diversity, and overspending. This means that the spending habits of teachers in Tacurong National High School are oftentimes observed. This result suits the study of Marasigan et al. (2022) that a person's spending habits typically influence how they utilize money to meet their needs and achieve their goals, often without exercising strict control. In a study conducted by Kamil and Istaningsih (2020), lifestyle and financial literacy were identified as key elements significantly impacting spending habits. Consequently, an individual's spending can be categorized into personal and household expenses. Understanding consumer spending patterns becomes particularly crucial during a crisis, as emphasized by Brandtner et al. (2021).

Significant Relationship between Financial Attitude and Spending Habits

The low positive correlation, showing a meaningful association between the two variables at a statistically significant level, between Financial Attitude and Spending Habits. This result suits the study of Manchanda (2018), who establishes a notably low and inconsequential association between materialism and distrust. Materialistic individuals tend to eschew saving money for the future, which could suggest a relationship between financial attitudes (materialism and distrust) and spending habits but without a strong correlation. Jamilah et al. (2021), who emphasize the cognitive aspects related to social relationships, social prestige, and financial power, influencing financial attitudes. This was further proved by Fallaw (2021) highlights how financial attitudes emerge from experiences, emotions, beliefs, and behaviors, suggesting a connection between these attitudes and spending habits. Sabri et al. (2020) suggest that individuals' financial attitudes play a pivotal role in shaping their shopping and saving practices, ultimately impacting their spending habits. This suggests that attitudes towards money influence how individuals manage and allocate their financial resources, thus affecting spending behaviors.

Multiple Regression Analysis of the Financial Attitude Domains towards Spending Habits

Based on the regression analysis results presented in Table 4, it appears that none of the financial attitude domains have a significant influence on spending habits, as indicated by their non-significant p-values. This finding aligns with the perspective suggested by Kamil and Istaningsih (2020), who argue that factors beyond financial attitudes, such as situational factors or individual preferences, might play a more significant role in shaping spending habits. Therefore, it can be inferred that the relationship between financial attitudes and spending habits may not be strong or significant. Furthermore, Lusardi and Mitchell (2019), their research delves into generational differences in financial literacy and saving habits, which are closely related to spending habits. Analyzing these differences through multiple regression analysis can elucidate how financial attitudes influence spending behaviors across different age groups.

Conclusions

The result implies that the level of financial attitude of teachers at Tacurong National High School is moderate. It shows that the financial attitude of teachers at Tacurong National High School is sometimes observed.

The result indicates that the teachers' spending habits are high and oftentimes observed.

The result shows that there is a correlation between the financial attitude and spending habits of teachers at Tacurong National High School; hence, the first null hypothesis is rejected.

There is no single domain of financial attitude that influences the teacher's spending habits; therefore, the second null hypothesis is accepted.

Among the financial attitude indicators, power prestige has the lowest level, according to the results. This indicates that Tacurong National High School teachers' financial attitudes are just frequently observed; as a result, teachers should concentrate on managing their finances and improve their financial attitude.

Teachers at Tacurong National High School should establish and practice their spending habits, particularly about their financial demands, as indicated by their moderate degree of diversity and overspending. It is suggested by the researchers that teachers should work on managing their spending patterns.

The researchers advise teachers to carefully assess their financial condition before making any purchases since the study reveals a

correlation between their spending habits and their financial attitudes.

Future researchers who plan to undertake any connected research should look for additional indicators that have a substantial correlation with spending habits, as it appears from the results that none of the financial attitude domains have a major impact on spending habits.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

El Jhon V. Sanoy Jr.

Tacurong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Anjelica Dew O. Oro

Tacurong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Rachel Ruellen N. Zaide

Tacurong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Maria Ericka Cazzandra S. Fernandez

Tacurong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Jose T. Decena III

Tacurong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines